

Analysis of academic studies on vertiport

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <p>Keywords: Vertiport eVTOL UAM Bibliometric Analysis Traffic Congestion</p> <p>Received: 6 December 2024 Revised: 26 December 2024 Accepted: 27 December 2024</p>	<p>With the advancement of technology and evolving urban needs, many aircraft and automobile manufacturers, along with startups, are engaged in research and development of electric vertical takeoff and landing aircraft (eVTOL) to enhance Urban Air Mobility (UAM). Concurrently, studies are being conducted to identify suitable areas for the takeoff and landing of aircrafts, commonly referred to as vertiports. This study aims to provide a comprehensive evaluation of existing literature on vertiports and systematically map the findings. Given the limited number of studies in Turkish literature, this work serves as a valuable resource for future researchers in the field. The analysis encompasses 107 publications from 2018 to 2024, identified using the keyword 'vertiport' in the Web of Science database. Utilizing the bibliometric analysis tool Biblioshiny in R Studio, it was found that the majority of studies were published in 2023, with a notable increase in publications since 2018. The leading contributor in this field is Peng Wei, with most research originating in the United States, South Korea, and Germany.</p>

1. Introduction

The United Nations' "World Urbanization Prospects" report indicates a rapid escalation in the rate of urbanization on a global scale. As of 2018, the global urbanization rate was 55%, and it is estimated to increase to 68% by 2050 (Song & Yeo, 2021). This increase in urbanisation has resulted in significant traffic congestion in urban areas. Traffic congestion is recognised as a significant global problem (Lim & Hwang, 2019; Park, Kim, & Kim, 2022; Song, Yeo, & Moon, 2021; Wu & Zhang, 2021). The social and economic losses resulting from traffic congestion are well-documented (Song & Yeo, 2021). The predominant causes of this phenomenon have been identified as increased traffic accidents (Willey & Salmon, 2021), noise, and pollution (Song & Yeo, 2021). An increased waiting time in traffic results in time being spent inefficiently (Pradeep & Wei, 2019). Consequently, the time allocated for both work and rest are diminished (Willey & Salmon, 2021). Research in the United States has estimated that individuals spend an average of 99 hours per year on the road due to traffic congestion, with the associated costs reaching 88 billion US dollars annually (Choi & Park, 2022; Wu & Zhang, 2021).

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Urban Air Mobility (UAM) is an emerging transportation paradigm with the potential to address challenges posed by congestion (Lim & Hwang, 2019). The impact of this transition is anticipated to be favourable for the majority of the population (Jeong, So & Hwang, 2021). UAM is defined as a new mobility concept with the potential to reduce travel times and change travel patterns (Fu, Rothfeld & Antoniou, 2019). It is a novel mode of transport that does not aim to connect residential areas and airports to urban centres, promising enormous time savings under favourable conditions (Schweiger & Preis, 2022). The concept of UAM envisions the provision of safe, sustainable, affordable and accessible air transportation for passenger mobility, cargo delivery and emergency management within or passing through a metropolitan area (Yedavalli & Cohen, 2022). This novel transportation system is expected to alleviate congestion in urban areas (Pradeep & Wei, 2019). The highest demand for UAM is expected to be in high-density and space-constrained cities (Rice et al., 2022).

The development of UAM commenced with the advent of helicopter transportation in the 1940s (Pradeep & Wei, 2019; Li, 2022). The 1960s and 70s witnessed a surge in the field with the advent of turbine-powered commercial helicopters (Vascik, 2017). In the 1940s, a significant number of helicopter flights were operated within the cities of New York and Los Angeles, primarily for the purpose of commercial passenger and mail transportation (Pradeep & Wei, 2019). From 1947 to 1971, Los Angeles Airlines utilised helicopters for the transportation of individuals and mail between various locations within the area (Pradeep & Wei, 2019). Concurrently, from 1949 to 1979, New York Airways utilised helicopters to facilitate passenger transportation between Manhattan helipads and airports in the New York metropolitan area (Li, 2022). The advent of helicopter air carriers can be traced back to 1947, when they emerged as air mail services, supported by subsidies from the US government (Vascik, 2017). In 1953, New York Airways became the first scheduled helicopter airline to carry passengers in the US (Medium, 2020). From 1953 to 1979, New York Airways utilised helicopters to facilitate passenger transportation between Manhattan and the three primary airports in New York: LaGuardia Airport (LGA), John F. Kennedy International Airport (JFK), and Newark Liberty International Airport (EWR). One of the earliest endeavours to establish an on-demand air transportation service occurred in the 1960s, when Air General introduced a system of on-demand flights utilising over 70 helipads in the city of Boston (Ale-Ahmad, 2022). These helipads were located in motel parking lots and private green spaces. A distinctive feature of Air General's operation was its reliance on a reservation system that enabled passengers to request flights with a minimum lead time of 30 minutes. Consequently, it is regarded as a pioneering instance of the concept of UAM, otherwise termed on-demand mobility (Vascik, 2017). However, these services were discontinued in Los Angeles in 1968 and New York in 1977 due to several accidents caused by mechanical failure (Garrow, German & Leonard, 2021; Pradeep & Wei, 2019). By the 1980s, helicopter VTOL services had ceased to operate due to elevated operational expenses, noise pollution, and the unfortunate occurrence of accidents (Glaudel, 2021; Gouveia, 2022). Globally, several companies focusing on designing eVTOL aircraft have invested more than \$2 billion in this sector (Garrow, German, & Leonard, 2021). Table 1 lists some companies operating in this market.

Table 1: Firms operating in the eVTOL market

Term	Authors
NASA, Uber	Lim & Hwang, 2019; Park, Kim & Kim, 2022; Song & Yeo, 2021
Airbus, Boeing	Chen, 2019; Song, Yeo & Moon, 2021
Ehang, Bell, Hyundai Motors, Lockheed Martin	Song, Yeo & Moon, 2021
Leonardo, Lilium, Terrafugia	Pradeep & Wei, 2019
EHang, Jobby Aviation, Zee.Aero	Pradeep & Wei, 2018
Cezeri3	Yavaş & Yavaş Tez, 2021
AirCar	AirCar, 2024
Embraer, Kitty Hawk, Pipistrel, Volocopter ve Aurora Flight Sciences	Kleinbekman, Mitici & Wei, 2020

Source: Produced by the authors

UAM represents a novel mode of transportation that has not previously existed. In order to support this mode of transportation, infrastructure must be in place. The designated area for this infrastructure is

referred to as a vertiport (Wiley & Salmon, 2021). In essence, vertiports are analogous to airports, serving as designated areas where eVTOL aircraft can take off and land. They also offer amenities such as line maintenance and battery charging and replacement services (Savaş & Gökşen, 2023). The design of vertiports should encompass not only the takeoff and landing processes but also the integration of various services that passengers may require (Jeong et al., 2021). The necessity for vertiports is paramount to ensure the efficient operation of the UAM system (Schweiger & Preis, 2022).

This study is significant in that it reveals the development of literature on vertiports. The paucity of studies on this subject in Turkish literature is significant in terms of providing a valuable source for researchers in this field. The study is structured into five chapters. The introduction of the study provides general information, while the second chapter presents the conceptual framework. The third chapter provides information about the methodology of the study, and the fourth chapter presents the findings of the study. The final chapter offers a conclusion and puts forward several suggestions.

2. Theoretical Background

In the past, helicopters were utilised for UAM operations; however, they were decommissioned in the late 1970s due to elevated operational costs and noise pollution. Contemporary projections, however, anticipate a resurgence in the utilisation of such aircraft, attributable to the advancements in technology and the increasing traffic density. Furthermore, there is a growing trend of organisations producing quieter and more environmentally friendly aircraft through the utilisation of electric power. Vertiports are essential infrastructure for the operation of eVTOL aircraft, facilitating take-off and landing (Kleinbekman et al., 2020). A vertiport is defined as the area where eVTOLs take off, land, and charge their batteries (Witter, 2022), and it is considered to be very important in terms of the efficiency of the UAM system (Rimja & Tirani, 2021). While there is a consensus in the literature on the necessity of designated landing and takeoff areas for UAM aircraft, there is no consensus on the nomenclature to be assigned to these areas. While a significant number of studies in the relevant literature utilise the term "vertiport", others employ varying terminology. The full list of these terms can be found in Table 2.

Table 2: Terms used instead of vertiport in the literature

Term	Authors
Vertiplaces, VTOL portlari, vertibase, vertistation, vertipad	Schweiger & Preis, 2022
Vertistop	Wiley & Salmon, 2021
VoloPort, urban-airport	Schweiger & Preis, 2022 Schweiger & Preis, 2022
Pocket airport, skypark, sky node ve sky port	Schweiger, Knabe & Korn, 2022

Source: Produced by the authors

Smaller and less capable vertiports are often referred to as vertistops, although vertiports and vertistops are sometimes collectively referred to as vertiports (Wiley & Salmon, 2021). The infrastructure supporting urban VTOL operations is defined as vertiports, defined as "VTOL hubs with charging infrastructure with multiple take-off and landing pads," and vertistops, defined as "a single take-off and landing pad with minimal infrastructure" (Schweiger & Preis, 2022).

A multitude of factors must be given full consideration during the developmental process of UAM. These include public acceptance, safety, planning, airspace management and operations (Yedavalli & Cohen, 2022). Consequently, academics conducting research on this subject are addressing these issues. Notable studies in this area include those by Abdellaoui, Naser & Stasicka (2013), Cummings & Mahmassani (2023), Kotwicz HERNICZEK & German (2022), Vascik & John Hansman (2021), and Öreg & Shin. The subject of UAM traffic flow has been explored by Cummings & Mahmassani (2021), while fleet size has been examined by Kang & Kim (2023). Other studies have focused on vertiport network design (Yedavalli & Cohen, 2022), human factors challenges (Scheff et al., 2020; Panesar et al., 2021), emissions (Mudumba et al., 2021), and public trust and acceptance (Chancey & Politowicz, 2020). As demonstrated in the works of Park, Park, Park, Park & Chun (2022) and Fu & Moeckel (2024). Karami et al, 2024), transportation mode preference (Fu, Rothfeld & Antoniou, 2019), demand (Ale-Ahmad & Mahmassani, 2023) and systematic review of demand (Long et al,

2023), aerodynamics (Jiang, Zhou & Ho, 2023), urban air logistics (Rifan, Adikariwattage & Barros, 2023), flight control design (Qu, Zhu, & Shan-Min Swei, 2022), UAM design specifications (Chun et al. The following papers were consulted: 2022), structural strength composite (Ishfaq, Nguyen, & Greenhalgh, 2023; Coenen, Malarkey, & MacKenzie, 2023), noise (Afari & Mankbadi, 2023; Greenwood et al., 2022), and UAM simulation enabling modelling of infrastructure, vehicles, network and operations (Rothfeld et al., 2018). In addition to air traffic flow and capacity management, studies on demand forecasting, trajectory, and cost modelling have been conducted in the field of vertiports (Niklaß et al., 2020).

In their 2019 study, Lim and Hwang applied the concept of vertiport location selection to the Seoul Metro Area. In contrast, Zelinski (2020) asserts that the availability of suitable locations for vertiport construction in metropolitan areas is limited. In response, he has proposed a range of vertical design configurations. Jeong, So, and Hwang (2021) created a noise-prioritized route to determine the locations of the vertiports for the operation of the UAM in the Seoul metropolitan area. The route was delineated utilising Matlab, and the vertiport location and noise analysis were conducted. Choi and Park (2022) examined the economic feasibility of UAM from two perspectives. Firstly, they estimated the cost of UAM services to attract customers. Secondly, they reviewed the operational policies to improve the economic feasibility of UAM services. Yedavalli and Cohen (2022) presented a simulation methodology to model potential vertiport locations in the San Francisco Bay Area. In a related study, Wu and Zhang (2021) utilised integer programming to determine the optimal locations for vertiports and to allocate users to these locations. Schweiger et al. (2022) focused on developing vertidrome airside operations. Willey and Salmon (2021) proposed a methodology for the design of urban air mobility networks. Taylor et al. (2020) identified the need for a 5-node network with 70 vehicles, three landing pads, and two UAM vehicle parking lots. With an investment of 160 million dollars, a vertiport serving 369 flights per day can achieve a break-even point in two years, with a Return on Investment of 122%. In a related study, Chen (2019) proposed a joint scheduling methodology to address optimal routing and charging tasks for an Autonomous Electric Air Vehicle System. Pradeep and Wei (2018) conducted a study on the arrival sequencing and scheduling for an eVTOL aircraft in the context of on-demand urban air mobility. In this study, the eVTOL aircraft sequencing and scheduling problem is formulated in the context of UAM for a mixed eVTOL fleet expected to land on a vertiport with a single landing area. Bulusu et al. (2021) developed a traffic demand analysis method to estimate the maximum number of people who can utilize UAM in a metropolitan area.

3. Methodology

In this study, bibliometric analysis, a systematic literature review method, was utilised. The bibliometric analysis was performed on 107 scientific studies obtained using the keyword vertiport in the Web of Science (WoS) database, which was determined within the scope of the research topic. Bibliometric analysis is defined as the analysis of studies published on a specific subject using statistical and mathematical methods (Erkan, 2020). The utilisation of bibliometric analysis enables the examination of scientific studies from a more expansive perspective (Hotamışlı & Erem, 2014). The concept was first introduced by Pritchard. The concept was expressed as a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the literature to monitor the development of a research area over a long period of time (Arıcı & Pelit, 2021). The analysis was conducted utilising the R programming language. The R programming language was developed by John Chambers and his colleagues in the 1960s for use in statistical calculations (Köse & Kurutkan, 2021). The Bibliometrix package, an integral component of the R program, was developed by Aria and Cuccurullo (2017) with the primary objective of systematically classifying, analysing, and mapping a substantial volume of intricate publications by leveraging its comprehensive data aggregation capabilities.

In this study, 107 publications that appeared in the Web of Science database between 2018 and 2024 and which contained the concept of "vertiport" in the title, abstract and keyword were saved to the computer as BibTeX. The resulting BibTeX file was then uploaded to the program using the "biblioshiny bibliometrix" package in RStudio. The programme yielded data on the number of authors, authors with the most publications, year of publication, country of publication, and journal of publication. These data were then examined within the framework of the variables.

4. Results and Discussion

A search of the Web of Science database using the keyword vertiport yielded 108 publications. The initial publication, dating back to 1998, was excluded from the present study due to its divergent evaluation approach from the contemporary utilisation of the vertiport concept. Initially, the study's findings were characterised in terms of their general attributes. In this context, the results of the analysis conducted using the Rstudio program indicate an annual growth rate of publications between 2018 and 2024 of 39.39%. This figure indicates that the subject is contemporary, and the number of publications is increasing on a daily basis. A further analysis of academic studies on vertiports, as published in the Web of Science database, involved 306 researchers. The analysis revealed an average of 7.63 citations per publication per year. The analysis also revealed the use of 347 distinct keywords. A total of 3,268 references were used in all the publications.

In this study, the process from the date of the first publication using the keyword vertiport was analysed. The predominant analytical technique in bibliometrics is citation analysis. This analysis employs citation counts as a metric to gauge the similarity between documents, authors, and journals. The analysis of citations can be further subdivided into two distinct approaches: bibliographic linkage and cocitation analyses. Examples include author linkage, author co-citation, journal linkage, and journal co-citation (Cuccurullo & Cuccurullo, 2017). The number of studies and citations from 2018 to 2024 is presented in Figure 1. The initial study in this domain was conducted in 2018, and it was observed that the number of publications was minimal in the initial years, with a subsequent increase as time progressed. The most significant escalation in the number of publications and citations was observed in 2021.

Figure 1: Number of academic publications on vertiport in web of science database by years

Source: Reproduced from Web of Science database.

In the Web of Science database, there are 265 citations to 22 publications in 2024, 297 citations to 34 publications in 2023, 156 citations to 18 publications in 2022, 48 citations to 22 publications in 2021, 26 citations to five publications in 2020, 20 citations to three publications in 2019, and one citation to three publications in 2018. It can be stated that the concept is very up-to-date, and the number of publications is increasing. The fact that eVTOL manufacturers have not yet put their air vehicles on the market and the criteria for vertiport design have not yet been determined have attracted the attention of academicians conducting research in this field. Thus, the number of studies on this subject is expected to increase. Most publications and citations will be published in 2023. As 2024 has not yet been completed, the number of citations has been lower than 2023. However, the number of citations is predicted to increase with an increase in the number of studies in the field. Similarly, a graph showing the annual number of scientific productions in the RStudio program is given in Figure 2. In this graph, it can be seen that the number of scientific productions increases regularly. As 2024 has not yet been completed, the number of scientific productions is lower in the graph compared to 2023. However, it is believed that the number of academic studies will increase at the end of the year.

Figure 2: Number of annual scientific production related to vertiport by years in web of science database

Source: Generated from the RStudio program.

As illustrated in Table 3, the most frequently cited studies, according to the number of citations received by studies on vertiport by the authors in the Web of Science database, are identified. The most frequently cited authors were Garrow, German, and Leonard, with 105 citations. The authors compared the concept of UAM with that of electric and autonomous vehicles used for land transportation. The subsequent most frequently cited authors are Kleinbekman, Mitici, and Wei, who, in their 2018 study on ranking and planning for eVTOL aircraft in on-demand urban air mobility, received 90 citations.

Table 3: Citation numbers of authors in Web of Science Database

Author	Publication Name	Number of Citation
Garrow, German & Leonard (2021)	Urban air mobility: A comprehensive review and comparative analysis with autonomous and electric ground transportation for informing future research	105
Kleinbekman, Mitici & Wei (2018)	eVTOL Arrival Sequencing and Scheduling for On-Demand Urban Air Mobility	90
Lim & Hwang (2019)	The Selection of Vertiport Location for On-Demand Mobility and Its Application to Seoul Metro Area	43
Wu & Zhang (2021)	Integrated Network Design and Demand Forecast for On-Demand Urban Air Mobility	41
Schweiger & Preis (2022)	Urban Air Mobility: Systematic Review of Scientific Publications and Regulations for Vertiport Design and Operations	38

Source: Reproduced from Web of Science database

The journals in which the five most frequently cited publications mentioned in Table 3 were published are listed in Table 4. The most frequently cited study was published in the Transportation Research Part C-Emerging Technologies. This journal is classified as a Q1 journal, according to the impact factor of ketagorilene. The second most frequently cited study was presented at a conference. The first Digital Avionics Systems Conference (DASC) was held in 1975. The 43rd conference in this series was held this year. These conferences offer a valuable opportunity for researchers seeking to establish connections within the field. Researchers are also advised to examine journals in which the most cited studies are published, in order to submit their own work for peer review.

Table 4: Journals in which the most cited studies are published

Author	Journal Name
Garrow, German & Leonard (2021)	Transportation Research Part C-Emerging Technologies
Kleinbekman, Mitici & Wei (2018)	IEEE/AIAA 37th Digital Avionics Systems Conference (DASC)
Lim & Hwang (2019)	International Journal of Aeronautical and Space Sciences
Wu & Zhang (2021)	Engineering
Schweiger & Preis (2022)	Drones

Source: Reproduced from Web of Science database

Of the academic studies published in the Web of Science database, 70 were articles, 34 were proceedings, and 2 were review articles. The houses with the highest number of publications on vertiport in the Web of Science database are listed in Table 5. IEEE has the highest number of publications in this field, with 33 publications. By examining these publication groups, it guides researchers who will work in this field where they can publish their studies. The Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) has been a database that includes all periodicals and conference proceedings since 1988. It also includes selected articles from journals and conferences published between 1950-1988 (Ulakbim, 2024). Another journal group with the highest number of publications is MDPI, which includes 447 refereed journals and 9 conference journals. MDPI, a pioneer in open-access publishing, has been supporting academic communities since 1996 (MDPI, 2024).

Table 5: Journals with the most publications in Web Of Science Database

Journal Name	Number of Publications
IEEE	33
MDPI	21
Elsevier	20
Springer Nature	8
Amer Inst Aeronautics Astronautics	5

Source: Derived from WoS database

As illustrated in Table 6, the journals in which the publications obtained as a result of the search using the keyword vertiport in the WoS database were published the most can be identified. The majority of these publications were presented at the Digital Avionics Systems Conference. The International Journal of Aeronautical and Space Sciences emerged as the leading journal, with a total of six publications. It can be concluded that researchers stand to benefit from these publications when undertaking journal selection.

Table 6: Journals with the most publications with the keyword vertiport

Journal Name	Number of Publications
2023 IEEE/AIAA 42nd Digital Avionics Systems Conference, DASC	9
International Journal of Aeronautical and Space Sciences	6
Drones	5
Transportation Research Part C-Emerging Technologies	5
Applied Sciences-Basel	4
Sustainability	4

Source: Generated from Rstudio program

Information on researchers who made at least three publications with the keyword vertiport in the WoS database is presented in Table 7. According to this, most publications were published by Kim SH, with eight studies. This was followed by Wei P and Lee J, with six and five publications, respectively. It is important for researchers to recognize authors working in this field and collaborate in the future.

Table 7: Researchers with at least 3 publications

Author	Number of Publications
Kim SH	8
Wei P	6
Lee J	5
Bridgelall R	4
Kim J	4
Preis L	4
Schweiger K	4
Chae M	3
Gentile G	3
Knabe F	3
Lee H	3
Opromolla R	3
Park BT	3
Pradeep P	3
Song K	3

Source: Generated from Rstudio program

Figure 3 presents information regarding the researchers who have published a minimum of three papers containing the keyword 'vertiport' in the WoS database. It is evident that Kim SH is the researcher with the most publications in the field of vertiport. Ardainden Wei P is the second author with the highest number of publications on vertiport. It is recommended that researchers establish connections with academics who have published extensively in this field.

Figure 3: Number of academic publications on vertiport by author in Web of Science Database

Source: Derived from WoS database

A subsequent analysis of studies in the Web of Science database yielded a distribution of publications by region, as illustrated in Figure 4. The USA had the highest number of publications, with 46 publications. This was followed by South Korea (n = 25) and Germany (n = 15). While the USA has contributed the most to the literature on vertiport, Turkey has not made any contribution to the field of vertiport.

Figure 4: Distribution of publications in Web of Science Database by region

Source: Derived from WoS database

Table 7 presents the number of citations of publications in the WoS database by country. The USA received the highest number of citations, with 364. The Netherlands received 130 citations, while Korea received 128. In 2017, the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) adopted the concept of CST and invited research in this field, which has since led to a rapid increase in interest and development in this system (Wu & Zhang, 2021). In this context, it is noteworthy that the USA's status as a global leader in aviation, coupled with its strategic prioritisation of eVTOL production, may have influenced the observed citation trends. It is also noteworthy that the Netherlands, despite publishing fewer publications, has attained second position in the citation rankings with 130 citations. This can be attributed to the fact that the second most cited study

had 90 citations, and another study by the same authors had also been highly cited, thus propelling the Netherlands to the top of the most cited countries.

Table 7: Number of citations by country

Country	Number of Citation
USA	364
Holland	130
Korea	128
Germany	105
China	60
Italy	19
England	5
France	2
Pakistan	2

Source: Generated from Rstudio program

Figure 5 shows the cooperation between the countries in these studies. Most publications are published in the USA, and cooperation has been made with countries such as China, Germany, the Netherlands, Italy, and Brazil. Cooperation also exists between Singapore and Korea, Colombia and France, the UK and Spain, the UK and India, and Italy and the Netherlands.

Figure 5: Cooperation of countries (reproduced from RStudio)

The keywords employed in this study encompass information derived from the titles of words and phrases contained within the articles and titles of the reference records. The utilisation of keywords has been demonstrated to facilitate the summarisation of content, thereby enhancing its visibility within relevant publications (Kocabaş & Alkan, 2020). The R program bibliometrix package provides a word cloud, which is a useful visual representation for researchers. The size of each word in the cloud is indicative of the frequency with which the word is used (Erkan, 2020). The word cloud created using keywords determined by the authors is shown in Figure 6. The most frequently used words were urban air mobility, vertiport, and advanced air mobility.

Figure 15: Author collaboration density map (generated from Rstudio program)

5. Conclusion

Urbanization has been driven by population growth and migration from rural to urban areas in recent years. The concentration of the population in cities gives rise to a number of problems, including traffic congestion and environmental pollution. In addition to a range of alternatives, such as smart cities and smart transportation, the most innovative solution is UAM. Several companies are designing eVTOL air vehicles, which are expected to become commercialized by 2025. While these aircraft are being developed, discussions continue on the areas where they will land and take off. While some studies in the literature state that heliports will be utilized first, some studies try to define areas that will include landing, take-off, parking, and charging operations under the name of vertiport. Furthermore, while the term 'vertiport' is frequently employed to denote such an area, some studies have also utilized expressions such as 'vertistop', 'vertihub', 'sky port', 'vertiplaces', 'VTOL ports', 'vertibase', and 'vertistation'. Research on vertiports has concentrated on subjects including vertiport design and the selection of optimal locations.

In this study, bibliometric analysis, which is a systematic literature review method, was used. A bibliometric analysis was conducted to examine 107 scientific studies in the WoS database, which were determined within the scope of the research topic. In this study, 107 publications published in the WoS database between 2018 and 2024 containing the concept of "vertiport" in the title, abstract, and keyword were included in the bibliometric analysis. Analyses were conducted using the Bibliometrix package in RStudio. According to the results of the analysis, the annual growth rate was 39.39%. This number shows that the subject is up-to-date, and the number of publications tends to increase daily. Academic studies on the subject were conducted by 306 authors. On average, 7.63 citations were made per publication per year. 347 keywords were used. A total of 3,268 references were used in all the publications. The year in which most studies were conducted in the Web of Science database was 2023. It was determined that the country with the most studies was the USA. Peng Wei was the most productive author of this paper. Garrow, German, and Leonard's study was the most cited.

This study had some limitations. First, the topicality of the subject limited the number of publications in the literature. Owing to the low number of publications, it was not possible to visualize some data in the R program Bibliometrix package. Furthermore, given that vertiports are still in the development stage, there is currently no commercialised eVTOL aircraft. This has led to constraints in terms of resources, resulting in research remaining in a theoretical state. A further limitation was the restriction of data extraction to the WOS database. It is possible that alternative results may be obtained by conducting the analysis using data from other databases, such as Scopus, Elsevier, and Google Scholar. Furthermore, it is possible that new

studies published in the WoS database after the date of data extraction may yield different results in terms of the number of countries, citations, authors, keywords, and images produced.

This study provides a valuable resource for researchers specialising in vertiports, manufacturers of eVTOL systems, airport operators, and investors. In future, a new study could be conducted by including other terms that can be used instead of vertiports. The utilisation of visualisation software such as Vosviewer and Citespac in lieu of R is a potential avenue for future exploration. Moreover, the standardisation of terminology within the field could be a fruitful avenue for further study. Another suggestion is to conduct research from the sustainability perspective.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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